

Can we measure what we feel? Exploring relationships between tactile perceptions and surface physical properties

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1. Introduction

There is a growing interest among consumer goods manufacturers to be able to relate a product's physical properties to consumers' perceptions of a product. This would enable them to understand how their products are being perceived and be able to design or improve a product that would better communicate the product and brand values.

The study reported in this paper addresses this need and focuses on the touch experience of a product's surface texture. We investigated people's tactile perceptions of various surface textures and related the perceptions to the measured surfaces' properties.

In psychophysical literature, extensive studies were found on texture perceptions. Researches have identified two strong dimensions of tactual perceptions, *soft-hard* and *rough-smooth*, and a weak dimension, *sticky-slippery* (Hollins, et al., 2000). However, the approach to the relationships between physical properties and the perceptions of surface textures often work on a one-to-one basis. For example, Tiest and Kappers' research (2006) qualified two surface properties, compliance and roughness, and compared the values with subjective judgements. In their study, results from a compliance measurement were compared with perceptions of softness and physical roughness data were compared with roughness. Their results showed those subjects' perceptions of roughness and softness might depend on more than one physical parameter

of the stimuli, in some combined ways. However, their research did not go beyond this finding.

In an early experiment on friction, Ekman and his colleagues (Ekman, et. al, 1965) tested friction coefficient of seven surfaces including five sand papers, one cardboard and one ordinary paper. They were relating the friction coefficient values with roughness perceptions and found that roughness perception has a power function related to the surfaces' friction coefficient. Smith et. al (2002) tested friction forces and found that perceptions of roughness may have correlations with tangential stroking force rate.

Harper and Stevens' (1964) study on softness perception found that subjective softness judgements were related to the compliance of their test objects by a power function with exponent 0.8 and that hardness and softness judgements were reciprocally related.

Results from these studies provide solid evidence that people's tactile perceptions of surface textures are based on their subjective judgement of surface physical properties. However, when using the results to address the industry needs as stated earlier, two deficiencies lie in these studies. Firstly, no contexts were related to any of the studies. Context is important for an industrial application as the range of materials used in different industries varies and people's perceptions and preferences change as well, when they are presented with different products. For example, if we test surfaces for food packaging, a surface that is described as being rough may not be considered as rough if it were placed together with sand papers. A person may like a soft surface on his mobile phone, but may not like it on his desk top. Secondly, the studies' subjective and objective relations were approached on a one-to-one basis, whereas, in reality, a perception of a surface quality is an effect of combined judgements. One-to-one relations are not sufficient to be used as a guide for designing and manufacturing synthesized surfaces.

The study presented in this paper investigated people’s tactile perceptions of 37 surface textures in the context of food packages. Responses of the textures were assessed by rating against six adjective pairs: *warm-cold*, *slippery-sticky*, *smooth-rough*, *hard-soft*, *bumpy-flat*, and *wet- dry*. People’s preference of surface textures was assessed using *like-dislike*. Four physical measurements were carried out, namely surface roughness, friction coefficient, compliance and rate of heat transfer and the results were related to the results from the perception test. Correlation and regression analysis were carried out to identify relationships between one or more measured properties and the tactile perceptions and preference.

2. Methodology

The reported study used 37 surfaces as stimuli. The investigation of the surfaces includes three aspects of work: a self-report study, physical measurements and correlation and regression analysis, as shown in Figure 1. They are reported in Section 2.1-2.4.

Figure 1 Research method

2.1 Stimuli description

The 37 surface textures used in the study included three types of materials: (1) surfaces 1-22 were cardboards; (2) surfaces 23-31 were flexible materials; and (3) surfaces 32-37 were laminate boards. Among them, the cardboards and flexible materials were used for food packages and the laminate boards were included to expand the varieties of textures. As a result, the 37 stimuli covered a good variety of textures with different physical properties, e.g. roughness, hardness, and warmness.

The stimuli were cut into 11cm×8cm rectangular shapes and were numbered on a sticker at the back.

2.2 Self-report experiment

A self-report experiment was carried out to collect data on people's tactile perceptions of the 37 surface textures. The experiment was conducted in a neutrally-furnished room that we use for focus group and self-report studies. Figure 2 shows the table in the room with two wooden boxes designed for holding the surfaces. One side of each box was kept open and covered with a white cloth to obscure the view of subjects to the stimuli whilst still allowing them to feel the surfaces of stimuli.

Figure 2 Experimental set up

2.3 Physical measurements

Four physical measurements were carried out. Roughness, R_a (μm) was measured using a commercial stylus surface profilometer (RTH Form Talysurf 120L). Friction coefficients, rate of heat transfer and compliance were measured on rigs all using the same piezo-electric force platform (Kistler MiniDyn), shown schematically in Figure 4.

Figure 4. Schematic views of a) friction, b) heat transfer, c) compliance measurements

Roughness is quantified by the vertical deviations of a real surface from its ideal form. Roughness average, R_a (μm), used in the study is the most popular value for determining roughness of a surface. It simply describes the distribution of peaks and valleys on the considered surface.

For the friction measurement (a) the surface stimulus (sample) was fixed to the force platform. An experimenter pressed (load F_Y) and slid (load F_X) his/her finger tip against it. F_X and F_Y were recorded against time. The friction coefficient was obtained from F_Y/F_X .

Loads F_Y were in the range 0.5 to 3N. For the heat transfer measurement (b) an artificial, silicone rubber, fingertip was loaded on to the surface, without sliding ($F_Y = 1$ N). A thermocouple (TC) was embedded just within the tip. Before contacting the surface, the tip was heated by an internal cartridge heater to $32 \pm 0.2^\circ\text{C}$, which is the real fingertip temperature. Upon contact with 1N loading force on the surface, the change (fall) with time of the TC temperature was recorded. The maximum rate of change ($^\circ\text{C/s}$), which occurred at the start of contact, was taken as the measure of heat transfer. For the compliance measurement a soft rubber support was inserted between the surface and the force platform and the finger tip replaced by a steel ball of radius 7 mm. With 4N loading force, the ball's displacement d_Y with increasing load F_Y was recorded. The measure of compliance was empirically taken to be the value of d_Y (mm) for $F_Y = 3\text{N}$. In all cases, measurements were repeated several times and averages obtained.

2.4 Correlation and regression analysis

Correlation and regression analyses were conducted with SPSS 12.0, a commercial software package for statistic analysis. Data collected from the self-report experiment and the measurements were entered into a SPSS data file. Pearson's correlation was selected for correlation analysis. Average scores of the six adjective pairs, scores of people's preference and the four measurements were entered as variables. For the regression analysis, average scores of adjective pairs were selected one at a time as dependent variable and the four measurements were selected as independent variable. Four regression methods, Enter, Stepwise, Forward and Backward, (Brace, et al., 2006) were tried for all combinations of variables. It was found that using Enter method often built models with a higher R^2 value. R^2 is a value that is used to assess the goodness-of-fit of a model. The higher a R^2 value means the better a model. Therefore, results from the Enter method was recorded and reported in this paper.

3. Results

3.1 Self-report experiment

Eighteen completed questionnaires were collected. Ratings for each stimulus against the six adjective pairs were converted into scores -10 to 10. The first scale on the left was scored -10 and the last scale on the right was scored 10. For the preference scales, *like* was scored -10, *not sure* was scored 0, and *dislike* was scored 10. An Excel data file was created and assembled scored as a matrix X of order $(p, n) \times m$, where p was the number of subjects, n was the number of stimuli and m were average scores of the six adjective pairs. A consolidating function was used to calculate average values of the 18 subjects' scores for stimuli against adjective pairs. Appendix A is a table of the average scores from the self-report experiment.

3.2 Physical measurements

Average values of the four measurements were recorded in Appendix B. They were used in to identify relationships with the results from the self-report experiment and as independent variables for the regression analysis.

3.3 Correlation and regression analysis

Correlation analysis

Correlation analysis created an 11×11 matrix illustrating the relationships between individual variables, shown in Tables 1. In the tables, only correlations at a significant level ($p < 0.01$) were shown. A negative sign in front of the correlation coefficient indicate negative relations between two variables. The absolute value between 0-1 indicates the strength of correlation. Figures in the white area are significant correlation coefficients between word pairs; figures in the grey area are coefficients

between word pairs and measurements; figures in the black area are between measurements. Figure 5 is a diagram illustrating the relationships between subjects' preference, perceptions of word pairs, and the physical measurements.

	<i>Smooth-rough</i>	<i>Hard-soft</i>	<i>Slippery-sticky</i>	<i>Warm-cold</i>	<i>Bumpy-flat</i>	<i>Wet-dry</i>	<i>Like-dislike</i>	Roughness, Ra	Compliance	Friction coefficient	Thermal property
<i>Smooth-rough</i>	1										
<i>Hard-soft</i>		1									
<i>Slippery-sticky</i>			1								
<i>Warm-cold</i>		-.737		1							
<i>Bumpy-flat</i>	-.974				1						
<i>Wet-dry</i>	.654		-.450		-.594	1					
<i>Like-dislike</i>							1				
Roughness, Ra	.719				-.668	.503		1			
Compliance		.953	.428	-.600		-.522			1		
Friction coefficient	-.442		.561		.427	-.773			.487	1	
Thermal property		-.931		.729					-.903		1

Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 1 Correlation matrix of the tactile responses and the measurements

Figure 5 Correlations between preference, adjective pairs and physical measurements

For relationships between the responses of word pairs, *smooth-rough* and *bumpy-flat* were found to have very strong negative correlation; *hard-soft* and *warm-cold* were found to have strong negative correlation; and *wet-dry* was found to have correlation with *smooth-rough*, negative correlation with *slippery-sticky* and *bumpy-flat*.

For relationships between people's preference and the perceptions of the six adjective pairs, we can see that subjects' preference (*like*) has positive correlations with *slippery* and *hard*.

For relationships between the responses of word pairs and the measurements, all six adjective pairs were found to have significant correlations with more than two measurements: (1) the perception of *warm-cold* was significantly related to a surface's thermal property and compliance; (2) the perception of *slippery-sticky* was significantly related to a surface's friction coefficient and compliance; (3) the perception of *smooth-rough* was significantly related to a surface's friction coefficient and roughness; (4) the perception of *hard-soft* was significantly related to a surface's thermal property and compliance; (5) the perception of *bumpy-flat* was significantly related to a surface's friction coefficient and roughness; and (6) the perception of *wet-dry* was significantly related to friction coefficient, roughness, and compliance.

Regression analysis

Correlation analyses explored linear relationships between two individual variables. We found that perceptions of an adjective pair have relations with more than one measured physical property. To explore the strength and the form of combinations of these physical properties contributing to a perception, regression analysis was performed. Six significant models ($p < 0.001$) were created using enter method. Table 2 presents the standard coefficients of measured properties that significantly entered the models

($p < 0.05$). A negative sign indicates a negative relation between the right-hand end of an adjective pair, i.e. *cold*, in *warm-cold*, and a measured property. The absolute value indicates the strength of a measured property contributing to the perception of an adjective pair. The bigger the value indicates the more influential the measured property to the perception of a surface texture. R^2 values are also given which is a measure of the goodness-of-fit of the models. Other important statistical values of the models are given in Appendix B, which include adjusted coefficients of determination (adjusted R^2), regression coefficients (B) and significant (p) values.

	<i>Warm-Cold</i>	<i>Slippery-Sticky</i>	<i>Smooth-Rough</i>	<i>Hard-Soft</i>	<i>Bumpy-Flat</i>	<i>Wet-Dry</i>
R^2						
	0.595	0.557	0.546	0.944	0.481	0.720
Standardized coefficient, Beta						
Thermal property	0.911			-0.355		
Compliance		0.920		0.676		-0.549
Friction Coefficient		0.765		-0.107		-0.560
Roughness		0.522	0.621		-0.561	0.261

Table 2 Relations between perceptions and measurements

From Table 2, the following observations were made:

- The four measured properties explained 59.5% of variation for the perception of *warm-cold*. Thermal property was found to have significant impact on this perception. A surface with high heat transfer rate is likely to be perceived as being *cold*;
- The four measured properties explained 55.7% of variation for the perception of *slippery-sticky*. Three measured properties, compliance, friction coefficient and roughness, have significant impact on this perception. Among them, compliance is the main factor that affects a person's perception of *slippery-sticky*. A surface with high

compliance, friction coefficient and measured roughness is likely to be perceived as being *sticky*;

– The four measured properties explained 54.6% of variation for the perception of *smooth-rough*. Roughness was found to have significant impact on this perception. A surface with high roughness value is likely to be perceived as being *rough*;

– The four measured properties explained 94.4% of variation for the perception of *hard-soft*. Three measured properties, thermal, compliance and friction coefficient, have significant impact on this perception. Among them, compliance is the main factor that affects a person's perception of *hard-soft*. A surface with high compliance, low friction coefficient and low roughness is likely to be perceived as being *soft*;

– The four measured properties explained 48.1% of variation for the perception of *bumpy-flat*. Roughness was found to have significant impact on this perception. A surface with high roughness value is likely to be perceived as being *bumpy*;

– The four measured properties explained 72% of variation for the perception of *wet-dry*. Three measured properties, compliance, friction coefficient and roughness, have significant impact on this perception. Among them, compliance and friction coefficient are two main factors that equally affect a person's perception of *wet-dry*. A surface with low compliance, low friction coefficient and high roughness is likely to be perceived as being *dry*.

4. Discussion

Correlations found between responses to word pairs demonstrated that subjects' perceptions of a surface texture might have influence from one to another. For example, a negative correlation was found between *hard-soft* and *warm-cold*, which indicated that a *soft* surface was likely to be perceived as being *warm*; the positive correlation between

smooth-rough and *wet-dry* indicated that a *rough* surface was likely to be perceived as being *dry*, vice versa. For the strong correlation found between *smooth-rough* and *bumpy-flat*, Hollin (Hollin et. al, 2000) explained it as that *smooth* vs. *flat*, and *rough* vs. *bumpy* were treated as synonymous in the experiment.

Correlations found between responses to word pairs and physical measurements demonstrated that tactile perceptions had relationships with more than one surface property. For example, it was found that *warm-cold* had significant relationships with a surface's thermal property and compliance; *slippery-sticky* had significant relationships with a surface's compliance and friction coefficient; both *smooth-rough* and *bumpy-flat* had significant relationships with a surface's friction coefficient and roughness; *hard-soft* had significant relationships with a surface's compliance, friction coefficient and roughness.

This approach has taken previous psychophysical research on tactile perceptions a step forward by considering the combinations of surfaces' physical properties in relation to a perception. Regression models were created to illustrate the form of the combinations and the strength of each physical property in contributing to the six perceptions. Three models were found to have more than one properties having significant impact on the perceptions. For example, Table 2 shows that the model of *hard-soft* is the best to predict the perception using the four measured properties ($R^2=0.994$). The perception of hardness will increase as a surface's compliance increases, and the thermal property decreases. Friction coefficient, which did not show significant correlation with *hard-soft* in Table 1, only plays a small role in affecting the judgment of a surface's hardness. The model of *slippery-sticky* shows that the perception of slipperiness was influenced by three measured properties, whose impact on the perception was in a sequence of compliance, friction coefficient and roughness respectively. The *wet-dry* model shows that

compliance and friction coefficient have equal impact on the perception whilst roughness plays a small role on affecting this perception.

For surface preference, it was found that *like-dislike* had significant correlations with *slippery-sticky* and *hard-soft*, indicating that for the 37 surface textures, subjects preferred surfaces that felt *slippery* and *hard*.

A comparison of the correlation matrix (Table 1) and the regression models (Table 2) revealed an inconsistency among the results. Some strongly correlated items showed in Table 1 did not enter the regression models. For example, *warm-cold* was found to have a strong correlation with thermal property and compliance, but only the thermal property entered the regression model. *Smooth-rough* and *bumpy-flat* were found to have correlations with friction coefficient and roughness, but only roughness was entered their model. An explanation from a statistical point of view is that if two independent variables significantly correlated, it is likely that only one variable is sufficient to predict the results, when the entry of the other variable could not significantly improve the prediction. A correlation matrix of the four measure properties showed significant correlations ($p < 0.001$) between compliance and thermal measurements (0.903) and compliance and friction coefficient (0.487), which justified the explanation.

The study reported in this paper is at an early stage of research to explore the relationships between tactile perceptions and a surface's physical properties. At this stage, we cannot generalise the findings about the relationships and apply them to all surface textures. The reason is that we believe the change of certain elements of a study, e.g. context of the study, sample size, and the number of adjectives, will cause the change of certain correlations, especially those that were not strongly correlated. More experiments using a large variety of surface textures in different contexts will be carried out in the future studies to identify a stable pattern of the relationships.

5. Conclusions

A controlled study on tactile perceptions of 37 surface textures, in the context of food packaging, was reported in this paper. Results of the correlation study illustrated that one perception has relationships with more than one surface's physical and regression models demonstrated the form and strength of the combined contributions of these surface properties to the perception. Surface preference was assessed to provide incremental information on people's responses from an emotional level. Perceptions of slipperiness and softness were found to have equal impact on the preference of a surface. This study is an essential step towards the understanding of relationships between a surface's physical properties and consumer's affective responses, which aligns with industrial needs to be able to manufacture surfaces that would have desired affective impact on consumers.

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REFERENCE:

Brace, N., R. Kemp, and R. Snelgar (2006) *SPSS for psychologists : a guide to data analysis using SPSS for Windows (versions 12 and 13)*, Basingstoke: Palgrave Macmillan

Ekman, G., J. Hosman, and B. Lindstrom (1965) Roughness, smoothness, and preference: a study of quantitative relations in individual subjects. *Journal of Experimental Psychology*, 70(1), pp18-26.

Harper, R., and S. S. Stevens (1964) Subjective hardness of compliant materials.

Quarterly Journal of Experimental Psychology, 16, pp 204-215.

Hollins, M., S. Bensmaia, K. Karlof, and F. Young (2000) Individual differences in perceptual space for tactile textures: Evidence from multidimensional scaling. *Perception & Psychophysics*, 62(8), pp 1534-1544.

Smith, A. M., C. E. Chapman, M. Deslandes, J-S Langlais and M-P Thibodeau (2002) Role of friction and tangential force variation in the subjective scaling of tactile roughness. *Experimental Brain Research*, 144, pp 211-223.

Tiest, W. M. B. and A. M. L. Kappers (2006) Analysis of haptic perception of materials by multidimensional scaling and physical measurements of roughness and compressibility. *Acta Psychologica*, 121, pp 1-20.

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Appendix A. Results of the self-report experiment and the physical measurements

	<i>Warm-Cold</i>	<i>Slippery-sticky</i>	<i>smooth-rough</i>	<i>hard-soft</i>	<i>bumpy-flat</i>	<i>wet-dry</i>	<i>Like-dislike</i>	Thermal property, dT/dt (°C/s)	Friction coefficient	Roughness, Ra (mm)	Compliance (mm)
1	1.06	-3.94	-5.94	-1.67	7.44	5.44	-4.33	1.88	0.29	0.74	0.58
2	1.39	1.39	6.5	-2.56	-6.83	4.06	-0.67	2.07	0.26	13.02	0.60
3	-1.78	-2.56	4.44	0.78	-2.78	7.44	-5.89	1.60	0.23	3.10	0.65
4	-0.11	-4	-2.11	-0.11	2.78	6.22	-3.83	1.84	0.19	4.29	0.63
5	-0.33	-1.83	-0.72	0.28	2.56	6.28	-1.17	1.83	0.21	3.00	0.63
6	-0.56	-0.83	3.39	0.06	-1.72	6.94	1.89	1.85	0.22	3.97	0.75
7	-1.44	-2.28	3.83	-0.28	-2.22	7.22	-3.83	1.74	0.21	5.06	0.67
8	-0.56	-2	3.11	-0.78	-1.72	6.5	-0.72	1.85	0.22	4.22	0.65
9	-1.67	-2.67	2.89	0.83	-0.72	7.11	-4.39	1.80	0.21	2.70	0.67
10	0.39	-4.28	-7.39	0.28	8	2.83	-4.89	2.18	0.17	0.39	0.68
11	0.78	-5.72	-7.61	-1.22	8.11	4.11	-4.33	2.26	0.17	0.44	0.62
12	0.17	0.94	5.33	0.17	-3.44	5.06	-0.72	1.95	0.38	6.74	0.79
13	0.06	-0.82	-6.94	-1.78	8.5	0.61	-4.94	2.12	0.57	0.07	0.64
14	1.11	-1.28	-7.17	-2.67	7.56	1.11	-3.28	2.03	0.55	0.07	0.61
15	0.28	-2.11	-2.82	0.39	5.11	4.39	-6.94	2.04	0.19	2.04	0.69
16	-0.61	-1.83	-2.5	0.39	4.61	5.94	-4.28	2.03	0.24	3.83	0.65
17	-0.61	-1.89	-1.67	0.44	3.83	6.11	-5.94	1.96	0.23	4.26	0.66
18	-2.28	-0.89	-0.94	-0.33	2.11	4.44	-1.78	2.11	0.22	1.89	0.62
19	-0.83	-2.5	-1.94	0.94	4	6.56	-5.44	2.04	0.19	3.42	0.65
20	-1	-1.44	-5.11	0.61	6.06	4.11	-3.78	1.80	0.39	0.75	0.63
21	1.89	-1.83	1.94	-0.29	-3.17	3.78	0.89	2.11	0.21	0.77	0.64
22	-0.39	0.56	1.28	0.17	-3.11	4.11	-1.78	1.78	0.25	0.66	0.65
23	0	1.11	-6.89	7.17	8.44	-0.5	0.89	0.35	0.61	0.11	1.12
24	-0.89	0.06	-4.78	6.39	7.89	2	1.94	0.37	0.26	0.48	1.16
25	-1.67	0.72	-5.67	6.94	8.22	-0.11	0.89	0.35	0.37	1.97	1.15
26	-1.39	2.06	-7.22	6.17	8.17	-0.83	0.39	0.42	0.61	0.22	1.18
27	0.39	-2.89	-7	5.61	7.5	1.78	-3.83	0.61	0.26	0.59	1.08
28	-1.11	1.56	-6.33	6.17	8.44	-0.44	-0.67	0.40	0.84	0.62	1.07
29	1	2.28	-5.67	3.06	7.17	1.89	2.5	2.29	0.53	0.65	0.91
30	-1.22	-0.11	-4.94	4.28	5.83	2.28	-1.22	1.79	0.43	0.42	0.94
31	-1.89	2.5	1.61	4.72	0.11	2.61	2.44	1.31	0.45	3.83	1.11
32	3.72	0.39	0.22	-5.56	2.67	3.89	-2.28	3.11	0.26	2.01	0.43
33	4.83	-0.78	0.61	-4.67	1.33	4.28	-3.72	3.29	0.20	2.15	0.41
34	6.06	-3.39	-7.06	-5.44	8.72	3.44	-2.78	3.14	0.23	0.68	0.42
35	5.17	1.72	4.44	-6.39	-6.11	3	-2.78	3.16	0.33	0.40	0.47
36	3.5	0.72	1.22	-5.56	-0.33	4.78	-2.28	2.90	0.26	3.78	0.44
37	4.94	-2.61	-8.06	-5.28	9.5	0.22	-4.28	3.17	0.53	0.05	0.47

Appendix B. Six adjective pairs' regression models

Adjective pair	Adjusted R ²	Variables	Coefficients, B	Significant (<i>p</i>)
<i>Warm-cold</i>	0.544	(Constant)	4.564	<i>p</i> =0.159
		Thermal (dT/dt)	2.437	<i>p</i> =0.002
		Compliance	1.165	<i>p</i> =0.670
		Friction coefficient	2.190	<i>p</i> =0.242
		Roughness (Ra)	-0.111	<i>p</i> =0.287
<i>Slippery-sticky</i>	0.502	(Constant)	-3.434	<i>p</i> =0.279
		Thermal (dT/dt)	1.907	<i>p</i> =0.011
		Compliance	8.256	<i>p</i> =0.004
		Friction coefficient	6.634	<i>p</i> =0.001
		Roughness (Ra)	0.311	<i>p</i> =0.004
<i>Smooth-rough</i>	0.489	(Constant)	5.935	<i>p</i> =0.400
		Thermal (dT/dt)	0.676	<i>p</i> =0.671
		Compliance	-.005	<i>p</i> =0.999
		Friction coefficient	-5.367	<i>p</i> =0.193
		Roughness (Ra)	1.105	<i>p</i> <0.001
<i>Hard-soft</i>	0.937	(Constant)	6.339	<i>p</i> =0.004
		Thermal (dT/dt)	-1.643	<i>p</i> =0.001
		Compliance	11.113	<i>p</i> <0.001
		Friction coefficient	-2.484	<i>p</i> =0.044
		Roughness (Ra)	-.075	<i>p</i> =0.263
<i>Bumpy-flat</i>	0.417	(Constant)	14.085	<i>p</i> =0.087
		Thermal (dT/dt)	-.593	<i>p</i> =0.745
		Compliance	1.527	<i>p</i> =0.824
		Friction coefficient	5.093	<i>p</i> =0.279
		Roughness (Ra)	-1.070	<i>p</i> <0.001
<i>Wet-dry</i>	0.685	(Constant)	22.242	<i>p</i> <0.001
		Thermal (dT/dt)	-1.130	<i>p</i> =0.099
		Compliance	-5.828	<i>p</i> =0.027
		Friction coefficient	-8.421	<i>p</i> <0.001
		Roughness (Ra)	.250	<i>p</i> =0.013